

Synthesis of 3,7-Disubstituted-4,6-dioxo-4*H*,6*H*-benzo[1,2-*b*:5,4-*b'*]dipyrans as Potential Antifeedants

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A number of diflavones¹, diflavanols² and dicoumarins³ derived from 4,6-diacetylresorcinol (1) have been shown to exhibit significant antifeedant activity. Recently we have reported⁴ the synthesis of 2,8-disubstituted-2,3,7,8-tetrahydro-4,6-dioxo-4*H*,6*H*-benzo[1,2-*b*:5,4-*b'*]dipyrans as potential antifeedants. Literature survey revealed that the synthesis and antifeedant activity of the title compounds have not been reported so far. The present investigation reports the synthesis of some new 3,7-disubstituted-4,6-dioxo-4*H*,6*H*-benzo[1,2-*b*:5,4-*b'*]dipyrans with a view to study the effect of isoflavone moiety on their antifeedant activity. Farkas *et al.*⁵ reported the synthesis of a number of isoflavones by the oxidative rearrangement of chalcones using thallium(III) nitrate in methanol via 1,2-diaryl-3,3-dimethoxypropan-1-ones. This method was adopted for the synthesis of the compounds.

samples^{2,6,7}. A suspension of the dichalcones (2*a-d*) in anhydrous methanol was stirred with thallium(III) nitrate trihydrate for 5 h. The resulting methanolic solution containing the diacetal (3) was refluxed with 10% HCl on a steam-bath for 5 h. Removal of the solvent gave a mixture containing the starting material and two other compounds. Hence it was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Benzene-CHCl₃ (7 : 3 v/v) elutions yielded 5 in 37–52% yields (5*a*, m.p. 182°; *b*, 224°; *c*, 258°; *d*, 244°). Methanol elutions furnished the diisoflavones (4) in average yields (4*a*, m.p. 204°; *b*, 292°; *c*, 282°; *d*, 266°). The diisoflavones exhibited strong ir absorption at 1 635–1 644 cm⁻¹ due to carbonyl group. The uv-spectra of these compounds showed two bands at 276–282 and 328–331 nm. The ir and uv spectra were in conformity with that reported for isoflavones⁸.

As a representative case, the spectral data of 4*a* has been discussed. The ir spectrum of 4*a* showed no absorptions in the region 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹, indicating the absence of phenolic OH groups but exhibited a strong band at 1 640 cm⁻¹ characteristic of carbonyl group of isoflavones⁸. The uv data, 280 nm (log ε 3.64) and 328 (4.24) are similar to those of isoflavones⁸. The ¹H nmr (200 MHz; CDCl₃) showed the characteristic peak of H-2 of isoflavones⁸ at δ 8.7 (2H, s, H-2 and 8). The H-10 and H-5 protons appeared as singlets at δ 7.8 and 8.0 respectively. Besides, the spectrum contained a multiplet at δ 7.3–7.8 (10H) which was assigned to the protons of the two pendent phenyl groups. The mass spectrum of 4*a* exhibited M⁺ at 366 (48%) and the observed fragmentation pattern was similar to those reported for isoflavones⁹. The other diagnostic ions were found at *m/z* 365 (M-H), 264 (10%), 183 (doubly charged ion, 10%), 149 (10%), 122 (20%), 105 (35%), 77(30%).

Compounds (4 and 5) were tested for their antifeedant activity by the non-choice test method¹⁰ using 6 h pre-starved fourth instar larvae of *Spodoptera litura* and the results indicate that compounds 4*b* and 5*b* only exhibited 100% antifeedant activity.

In 5*a*, the phenyl group is at C-2 instead of C-3; C-3 carries hydrogen.

The required starting materials, the dichalcones (2*a-d*) were prepared by the condensation of 4,6-diacetylresorcinol (1) with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of 60% aq. KOH and characterised by comparison with authentic

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